

Leadership and the Charles Handy Archetypes: Understanding the Role of the Leader

Liderança e os Arquétipos de Charles Handy: Compreendendo o Papel do Líder
El liderazgo y los arquetipos de Charles Handy: Entendiendo el papel del líder

Recebido
Received
Recibido
15 nov. 2023

Aceito
Accepted
Aceptado
20 mai. 2024

Publicado
Published
Publicado
28 jun. 2024

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e_ISSN
2965-3339

DOI
10.29327/2384439.2.3-4

São Paulo
v. 2 | n. 3
v. 2 | i. 3
Junho
June
Junio
2024

Hiego Andre de Medeiros¹
hiego.medeiros@fatec.sp.gov.br

Rebeca Santos de Sa¹
rebeca.sa@fatec.sp.gov.br

Vanessa Almeida Suzart dos Santos¹
vanessa.santos113@fatec.sp.gov.br

Lea Paz da Silva¹
lea.silva3@fatec.sp.gov.br

1 – Faculdade de Tecnologia da Zona Leste – Fatec Zona Leste

Abstract: This study addresses the role of leadership and the organizational culture of a company, relating them to Charles Handy's theory (1994), which focuses mainly on the archetypes of the Greek gods. With the aim of investigating the leadership style of a company in the logistics sector, located in the city of São Paulo and how this leadership may or may not affect the organizational climate and consequently the team's performance, this research sought to understand this leadership style in a to contribute to the improvement of the team. We identified studies on the topic in order to analyze these points in the company and in the leader we chose as the research object. Furthermore, observe how the employee sees the leader through a questionnaire that is an integral part of the chosen theory. In the end, we can conclude that to be a good leader you need to be constantly evolving, especially with regard to learning, in addition, we also conclude that there are archetypes of leaders that can guide an entire organization, impacting performance productively or not. of the company and its productivity.

Keywords: Leadership; Organizational culture; Team.

Resumo: Este estudo aborda o papel da liderança e a cultura organizacional de uma empresa, relacionando-os à teoria da Charles Handy (2012) que tem como foco principal os arquétipos dos deuses gregos. Com o objetivo de averiguar o estilo de liderança de uma empresa no ramo logístico, situada na cidade de São Paulo e como essa liderança pode afetar ou não o clima organizacional e conseqüentemente o desempenho da equipe, esta pesquisa buscou conhecer este estilo de liderança de maneira a contribuir na melhoria da equipe. Identificamos estudos sobre a temática de maneira a analisar esses pontos na empresa e no líder que escolhemos como objeto de pesquisa. Além disso, observar como o colaborador enxerga o líder por meio de questionário que é parte integrante da teoria escolhida. Ao final podemos

concluir que para ser um bom líder é preciso estar em constante evolução, principalmente no que se refere ao aprendizado, além disso, concluímos também que há arquétipos de líderes que podem nortear toda uma organização, impactando de forma produtiva ou não o desempenho da empresa e sua produtividade.

Palavras-chave: Liderança; Cultura organizacional; Equipe.

Resumen: *Este estudio aborda el papel del liderazgo y la cultura organizacional de una empresa, relacionándolos con la teoría de Charles Handy (2012) que se centra principalmente en los arquetipos de los dioses griegos. Con el objetivo de investigar el estilo de liderazgo de una empresa del sector logístico, ubicada en la ciudad de São Paulo y cómo este liderazgo puede o no afectar el clima organizacional y, en consecuencia, el desempeño del equipo, esta investigación buscó conocer este estilo de liderazgo con el fin de contribuir a la mejora del equipo. Identificamos estudios sobre el tema con el fin de analizar estos puntos en la empresa y en el líder que elegimos como objeto de investigación. Además, observa cómo el empleado ve al líder a través de un cuestionario que es parte integral de la teoría elegida. Al final, podemos concluir que para ser un buen líder es necesario estar en constante evolución, sobre todo en lo que respecta al aprendizaje, además, también concluimos que existen arquetipos de líderes que pueden guiar a toda una organización, impactando productivamente o no en el desempeño de la empresa y su productividad.*

Palabras clave: Liderazgo; Cultura organizacional; Equipo.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Chiavenato (2000, p 147), "leadership is the interpersonal influence exercised in a situation and directed through the process of human communication to achieve a certain objective." That said, leading corresponds to influencing people towards something and generally towards some objective in common with the team. Furthermore, for good leadership, there must be a style, and it must be compatible with his team.

Leadership plays a pivotal role in upholding a company's trust and integrity. It leverages the organizational climate to foster a conducive work environment. As per Chiavenato (2000), the organizational climate can be deemed favorable or unfavorable, as it is intricately linked to the quality of an organization's psychological environment. It underscores the significant responsibility that leaders bear in shaping the organizational climate.

Also, according to Costa (2021, p. 5), "the leader is the one who can generate reasons to drive the behavior of those led to self-motivation, contributing to the modeling of human behavior in organizations." Therefore, organizations must be increasingly committed to discovering whether their leaders are fulfilling the ideal of motivating their team. One of the main characteristics in the professional market is knowing how leaders influence the team so that good results are achieved within the organization.

This study will explore the bibliography on leadership, leadership style, and its archetypes. It will centrally focus on the archetypes of the Greek gods and their characteristics. Furthermore, we will discuss how the leader's profile can affect the organization and its climate.

Our primary aim is to investigate the leadership style of a company in the hospital materials logistics sector and its potential impact on the organizational climate. This research is crucial as it can provide insights into how leadership influences team dynamics and performance. By uncovering the effects of a leader's style on their employees, organizations can develop strategies to enhance their work environment and, ultimately, their productivity. The potential impact of this research on organizational productivity underscores its urgency and relevance.

2. LEADERSHIP: A NEW LOOK

One of the main characteristics in the market today is knowing how to work as a team. Furthermore, the search for leaders rather than bosses has increased. With this, the relevance of studies in the area and qualifications to stand out are seen. Therefore, we sought some studies on the topic to address in this report to identify these points in the company in question and the leader we chose as a model for the study.

According to Chiavenato (2000), organizations are made of people and for people. Therefore, it is crucial that individuals feel valued in all their differences. Working in a company involves living with people, each with their unique stories,

beliefs, and cultures. This understanding underscores the need for organizations to promote more group work, develop their teams, and manage people in the best possible way to achieve notable results.

In an organization, a team has shared goals, which are intrinsically linked to the leader's goals. To support this research, we selected the approach of authors Novo, Chernicharo, and Barradas (2008), who say that the team is "a group of people with complementary knowledge, committed to a purpose, performance goals, and common approaches, and through for which they remain mutually responsible." (NOVO; CHERNICHARO; BARRADAS, 2008, p 73). Therefore, for a team to be well-evolved, it is necessary to be clear about these objectives, purpose, and goals and thus also identify with them.

Furthermore, to have a good team, it is necessary to have a good leader, and he needs to exert influence over these people. With this, "leadership can be defined as a typically social phenomenon; it is the effort made to influence the behavior of others to achieve organizational, individual and personal objectives." (NOVO; CHERNICHARO; BARRADAS, 2008, p 29). Furthermore, the leader who wants to be effective in his leadership task must be responsible for achieving the goals he created for his team (COSTA, 2021).

A leader may encounter several challenges when trying to achieve a well-performing team. For example, being placed in an environment with wide diversity requires a certain flexibility from the leader to understand each member's needs and characteristics. Furthermore, to become inspiring, it is essential to identify and enhance the individual talents of his team (GOLEMAN, 2008).

Another essential aspect of good leadership is that a human leader is increasingly sought after nowadays. Therefore, leaders in contemporary society must abandon the mechanistic and bureaucratic vision of team management (CAVALCANTI, 2014). The author also comments on the importance of adapting people management to social and cultural changes to promote a healthy and productive work environment (CAVALCANTI, 2014).

Still, regarding team management, Cavalcanti (2014) states that open communication is a fundamental aspect, thus creating a relationship of trust and empathy with team members. Moreover, these people must be motivated daily for all these points to be worked out with a team. In addition to having a good leader, a leader who influences, listens, and executes the ideas stated above, it is necessary to build a bond of identification so that the team is motivated with their tasks. Therefore, we bring the statement of the authors Novo, Chernicharo, and Barradas (2008):

The search for motivation depends on the manager's ability to build a bridge of identification between individual objectives and organizational objectives, becoming an essential agent in

creating more favorable work climates, investing in people, making them capable of creativity, facilitating their arrival at self-realization and enabling them to envision a better future for themselves and the organization in which they work. (NOVO; CHERNICHARO; BARRADAS, 2008, p 111-112).

Good communication between the team and the leader and vice versa is necessary for the organization to have an environment of respect and outstanding achievements. Furthermore, the organization must promote this more open and communicative relationship, developing the leader and the members through lectures, dialogues, and continuous learning.

2.1. GODS AND LEADERSHIP STYLES

Archetypes in leadership are models or behavior patterns that represent different leadership styles. Our study and research will be based on the archetypes of the Greek gods and their influence on leadership today.

According to author Marqueze (1998), the Greek gods "represented characteristics with which humans identified, worshiping one or more of them according to their desires." Therefore, the gods were seen as examples to be followed and as models of behavior in society and, therefore, in their work environment. Thus, patterns of behavior emerge that can support leaders' decisions.

Handy (2012), in his work "Gods of Administration," discusses the characteristics of each god as an influence on the company's organizational culture. In this way, we have created some club culture, which consists of the gods and their ways of leading humanity.

Let us start with the Zeus club, a culture of significant value, especially for small companies. This culture is characterized by its emphasis on employee empowerment, freedom of action, and rewards. The Zeus of a large organization is often charismatic and is usually referenced for his achievements (MARQUEZE, 1998, p 85). This culture, where power is centralized, is a popular choice for small companies.

Then, we have the club of the god Apollo, known as the god of rules and order. In this culture, employees typically wait for instructions from their leaders, and if this does not happen, they may become lost. Power is concentrated at the top of the pyramid, making Apollo the Sun the center of everything (MARQUEZE, 1998).

Now, let us explore Athena's Club, a culture that places the highest value on the collaborator. Conflicts are minimal, as respect for each other's abilities is imperative, and rewards are shared (MARQUEZE, 1998, p 44). This culture,

which encourages every employee to contribute to problem-solving, tends to be short-lived, as it flourishes on the need for problems to be solved.

Finally, the Dionísio culture can be identified in organizations where employees are seen achieving their personal goals, "where talent and personal ability are the keys to success" (MARQUEZ, 1998, p. 48). We can sometimes see one or more gods in companies as a reference for leadership and organization.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Some methods were used to carry out this study, including bibliographical research, which allows us to go deeper into the topic, as it "allows the researcher to have broader coverage than if he were to research directly" (ZANELLA, 2011). Therefore, we selected some authors to use as a theoretical basis for our research.

In addition to bibliographical research, we used qualitative research with a case study. In this stage, we will approach, using a questionnaire, our two objects of study: the company leader and a company employee. According to the author Zanella (2011), the case study consists of an analysis of one or a few objects of study, seeking to understand their reality. Therefore, in this study, we used the questionnaire by Charles Handy (1994), a renowned author in the field of administration, who discusses archetypes of leaders such as gods from Greek mythology.

3.1. THE COMPANY

The company in this study is in the hospital materials logistics sector. It has been distributing hospital medical products and services for 40 years. He has expertise in business, processes, investments in technology, and the expertise to design, implement, and execute projects, ensuring cost-effectiveness and advantages, as well as Ultra logistics and intra-logistics processes—for example, the use of the KANBAN, KAIZEN, AND POKA-YOKE method. Being Kanban, an intra-logistics process that controls consumption without waste or shortages, ensuring traceability to the patient, Kaizen is the practice of continuous improvement through process improvements and is recognized throughout the world as an important strategic pillar of long-term competitiveness for organizations, and finally, Poka-Yoke (Which in Japanese means "Error-Proof") being the tool that the company uses to guarantee the quality of the services provided, the defined Kanban consumption pacts, processes from the Warehouse to the Hospital. The headquarters is in São Paulo, in the Brás region, and was founded in 2015.

3.2. LEADERSHIP ANALYSIS

The leader to be analyzed is a male, 46 years old, and his name is Jose Carlos da Silva (fictitious name). He has an academic background in the Logistics Technologist course and currently leads a logistics team at the company LOG (fictitious name) in São Paulo.

As a team leader for eight years, Jose Carlos has demonstrated a democratic

leadership style that is both inspiring and effective. He consults his team before making decisions, fostering a sense of commitment and satisfaction among the team members. His practical technical knowledge, problem-solving skills, and decision-making abilities further enhance his leadership.

Jose Carlos possesses a range of skills that make him an effective leader. He is adept at listening to his team members and managing internal conflicts, should they arise. While he can be authoritative, he values his team's ideas and is open to change. His strong interpersonal communication skills and ability to motivate his team members are vital to achieving good results.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research was based on the questionnaire in Charles Handy's book *Gods of Administration*, which discusses organizational culture. It was also supported by the author's analysis of archetypes, which the author also exposed. The author, Charles, relates these types to archetypes, such as the Greek gods, to identify the type of leader better. Therefore, each Greek God has his leadership style, and so to speak, each leader would have this archetype.

Our approach to the company LOG (fictitious name) and its leader, José Carlos (fictitious name), was crucial to our research process. We also incorporated the perspective of a collaborator (anonymous) to stimulate diverse discussions. In addition to the questionnaire, we conducted a thorough and comprehensive analysis according to the theories of Charles Handy, as follows:

The lower the total count for statements, the more prevalent that culture is in his organization. A count of 9 for the statements (a as low as possible) means a pure Zeus culture. It is unlikely you will get a total that low. (HANDY, 2012, pg. 81)

Our survey on the leader's profile and the employee's perspective was not just conducted but meticulously so. The answers, as shown in Figure 1, were recorded in Google spreadsheets, and calculations were prepared, with the leader's responses being the first to be analyzed.

Observing the leader's answers to the questionnaire made it possible to raise some ideas about his archetype. As the author Handy (2012) explains, there is a god for each letter, and we discover which leader comes closest when he selects it in the smallest quantity, as that is how much he identifies himself. For better identification, he created a scheme in which the number 1 represents Zeus, the number 2 represents Apollo, the number 3 represents Athena, and the number 4 represents Dionysus. We adopted the letters A, B, C, and D for our research, with the corresponding representations.

Therefore, when applying the questionnaire and developing the data collection and calculation, it was possible to identify that José Carlos's leadership style tends to resemble that of Dionysus, with the influence of Athena.

Figure 1. Leader Questionnaire

Questions	A	B	C	D
1	4	2	1	3
2	4	3	1	2
3	3	2	1	4
4	4	2	3	1
5	3	4	2	1
6	3	4	2	1
7	2	3	4	1
8	2	3	4	1
9	1	4	2	3
TOTAL	26	27	20	17

Source: Prepared by the authors (2023)

In Dionísio's leadership, according to Handy (2012), the organization is who works for the employee; because of this, employees tend not to recognize the power of the organization. Moreover, this influence of Athena brings a need to solve problems without centralizing power. Therefore, the ideal is to work in groups; even so, Handy (2012) observes that this model can end very soon because it does not adapt to crises.

So that we could understand whether the employees' vision of the leader would be the same, we asked an employee from José Carlos' team to answer the same questionnaire. To our surprise, we came across similar results, where the employee had the same vision as the leader himself about his archetype. Figure 2 shows the results of the employee questionnaire.

Figure 2. Employee Questionnaire

Questions	A	B	C	D
1	2	4	3	1
2	3	4	1	2
3	2	3	4	1
4	2	4	3	1
5	4	3	1	2
6	4	3	1	2
7	1	2	3	4
8	2	1	3	4
9	4	3	2	1
TOTAL	24	27	21	18

Source: Prepared by the authors (2023)

5. CONCLUSION

Our final considerations from the literature review and case study underscore the paramount importance of leaders' continuous evolution and learning. This adaptability is a cornerstone in successfully navigating the ever-changing landscape of organizational leadership. We also observe the presence of archetypal leaders who possess the ability to effectively steer an entire organization.

By applying the questionnaires, we identified the archetypes of the study leader and the employees' views of this leader. In both questionnaires, the Greek god Dionysus predominated. Therefore, this leader can be highly charismatic and motivating, inspiring others to follow his vision.

While the Dionysus archetype embodies intelligence and charisma, it also carries potential drawbacks. These include a lack of maturity and a temperamental attitude, which can hinder effective collaboration. Despite inspiring his employees, this leader may need help with mature problem-solving.

However, his profile is influenced by Athena. It could be a future solution, as it is an archetype of wisdom and responsibility for solving problems. The leader profile needs to be better worked on, but it has a direction to achieve great things in his team. This profile fits the company's size in the study, but care must be taken to keep employees motivated and engaged.

Employee motivation is intricately linked to their needs. When these needs are not met in their work environment, they are at risk of underperforming and losing motivation. Motivation is not something that can be simply imposed, but rather it needs to be nurtured and developed. It is one of the most crucial foundations for effective work within an organization. Furthermore, it is imperative to identify and implement actions that foster a better work environment for employees, where they have the freedom to be creative and feel more visible and valued.

REFERENCES

- CHIAVENATO, I. **Introdução à Teoria geral da administração**. Rio de Janeiro: Campus, 2000.
- COSTA, A B. **Liderança e Comportamento organizacional**. Secretaria de Pernambuco, 2021.
- CAVALCANTI, M. **Gestão de Pessoas: Abordagem Pós-Moderna**. Editora Atlas, 2014
- GOLEMAN, D. **Inteligência Emocional: A Teoria Revolucionária Que Define o Sucesso Pessoal e Profissional**. Editora Objetiva, 2018.
- HANDY, C. **Deuses da administração: Como enfrentar as constantes mudanças da cultura empresarial**. Editora Saraiva, 2012.
- MARQUEZE, M. **Uma metodologia simples para categorização de Cultura Organizacional: estudo de caso em empresa catarinense**. Florianópolis, UFSC, Programa de Pós-Graduação em Engenharia de Produção, 1998.

NOVO, DV; CHERNICHARO, EAM; BARRADAS, MSS. **Liderança de Equipes**. Rio de Janeiro: Editora FGV, 2008.

ZANELLA, L. C. H. **Metodologia de pesquisa**. UFSC - Departamento de Ciências da Administração. Florianópolis, 2011.